

METHODOLOGY FOR FORMING THE CONCEPT OF "I" IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN 6-7 YEARS OLD

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Annotation: This article comprehensively analyzes the process of formation of the concept of "I" in preschool children aged 6–7, its psychological and pedagogical foundations and possibilities of development based on modern methodological approaches. The article examines in detail how the components of the concept of "I" - such areas as a positive attitude towards oneself, independence, expression of one's own opinion, and understanding of social role - are formed in pedagogical practice. The author offers effective methods for strengthening the image of "I" through game technologies, interactive communication, dramatization, visual and pictorial activities, psychological training and role-playing games based on child psychology, stages of personality development and didactic principles.

Keywords: "I" concept, personal development, self-awareness, identity, methodology, playful activity, educational approach, psychological development, child psychology.

Introduction

With the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, fundamental reforms began in all areas, in particular in the education system, and this process found its clear expression in the modernization of the preschool education system. New political and legal frameworks, state programs and modern approaches created the basis for the comprehensive development of preschool children. The establishment of the Ministry of Preschool Education by the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3305 of September 30, 2017 was an important step towards the formation of this sphere as an independent system. This resolution set the main goal of "creating equal opportunities for the intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of children" [1].

Also, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Preschool Education and Training" of December 16, 2019 (ORQ-598) recognized preschool education as a stage aimed at personal development. This law specifically emphasizes such aspects as "social adaptation of the child's personality, development of

communicative abilities, and assistance in self-awareness” among the main tasks of preschool education [2]. This brings the issue of developing the child’s personal identity, that is, the concept of “I”, to the center of education and upbringing.

In psychological and pedagogical literature, the concept of “I” is interpreted as an internal psychological structure that is formed on the basis of children’s self-awareness, self-perception, self-evaluation, and comparison with others. L.S. Vygotsky's theory argues that a child's personal development occurs through the social environment, and shows that the formation of a sense of "self" is also associated with interaction and activity [3].

There are some studies in Uzbekistan in this area. In particular, G. Tulaganova (2020) covered the theoretical foundations of introducing a personal approach in preschool education, while M. Murodova (2022) studied the methods of forming socio-emotional competencies in preschool children. However, the impact of the concept of "I" on the psychological development of 6-7-year-old children and the methodology for its formation have not been systematically studied.

Therefore, this study develops methodological approaches aimed at forming the concept of "I" in 6-7-year-old preschool children, and evaluates their practical effectiveness. The scientific novelty of the work is that it systematically tests innovative game technologies, person-centered methods, and visual reflection techniques that serve to develop a sense of "self" and identifies opportunities for integration into the educational process.

The following studies were conducted to guide the formation of the concept of “I” in preschool children aged 6–7.

The object of the study was the personal development of preschool children aged 6–7. The subject of the study was methodological approaches aimed at qualitatively forming the concept of “I” and their pedagogical and psychological foundations.

The study was conducted in 2 state preschool educational organizations (PSEs) in the city of Urgench and the Khorezm region in the 2024–2025 academic year. A total of 40 children aged 6–7 were involved:

- Experimental group — 20 people (special methods were used);
- Control group — 20 people (continued in the form of traditional education).

Also, 4 pedagogues and 2 preschool psychologists actively participated in the experimental work.

The following scientific methods were used in the study:

Theoretical analysis - the psychological and pedagogical foundations of the concept of "I", existing experiences, foreign and domestic literature were studied.

Diagnostic methods - the following tools were used to determine the self-awareness, attitude to oneself and social position of children:

Dembo-Rubinstein methodology (determining the level of self-esteem of the child);

"I draw my image" technique (visual reflection of the child's image of "I");

Interviews and tests (psychological state is determined through personal questions, role-playing games).

Experimental and test work - a 12-week methodological impact program was implemented in the experimental group (given below).

Mathematical and statistical analysis - the results of the pre-experiment and subsequent ones were compared and analyzed using the t-test in the SPSS program.

A methodological impact program was implemented in the experimental group based on the following stages:

Stages	Activity content
Stage 1 (preparation, 1-2 weeks)	Observation of children, initial diagnostics, and establishing personal communication
Phase 2 (basic, 3-10 weeks)	Games aimed at self-awareness: "Who am I?", "What can I do?", "My feelings", "I will draw myself", "Me with other people"
Phase 3 (final, 11-12 weeks)	Re-diagnosis, comparison of results, individual recommendations

Methodological approaches were selected based on a person-centered approach. Attention was paid to working with each child individually. In the process of the activity, the emotional state of children, vocabulary, level of self-esteem, and communication skills with peers were monitored.

The study was conducted in accordance with the scientific and ethical norms of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

During the study, the state of formation of the concept of “I” in preschool children aged 6–7 years at the initial and experimental stages was compared. Diagnostics were carried out in the following areas:

- Level of self-esteem (Dembo-Rubinstein methodology);
- Clarity and consistency of the image of “I” (through visual-associative drawing analysis);
- Socio-emotional self-awareness (based on conversation, game techniques).

According to the initial diagnostic analysis conducted at the beginning of the study, the concept of “I” of children in the experimental and control groups was in the following state:

Diagnostic state view:

Indicator	Experimental group (N=20)	Control group (N=20)
High level	15.6%	17.9%
Intermediate level	37.4%	45.5%
Low level	56.0%	48.2%

These indicators showed that most children have a weak activity in self-awareness and the image of the "I" is not consistently formed.

The situation after the experiment

After 12 weeks of methodological approach, a significant increase in the concept of "I" was observed in the children in the experimental group. The results of repeated diagnostics were as follows:

Indicator	Experimental group (N=20)	Control group (N=20)
High level	51.26%	21.5%
Intermediate level	39.7%	46.4%
Low level	15.40%	38.2%

These changes were statistically analyzed using the t-test. The results of the analysis showed that there was a significant difference in the experimental group. In the control group, such changes were not statistically significant.

The analysis of visual-associative drawings was as follows:

The drawings obtained through the “I” image drawing exercises were analyzed in terms of content. Before the experiment, children often focused on

physical appearance or surrounding objects when expressing themselves, but after the experiment:

-Personal qualities (kind, wise, friendly, positive emotions) were more reflected;

-Signs indicating a positive attitude towards oneself (heart, sun, flower) appeared in the drawing;

-Personal "I" and social "I" (family, group role) were expressed together, and identification deepened.

The results of pedagogical observation were as follows

The observations conducted during the experiment showed that:

-Children began to express their opinions freely;

-Increased instances of participation in group activities on their own initiative;

-Positive identification increased through phrases such as "I do it myself", "I can help".

Thus, the results of the experiment showed that special methodological approaches (self-expression games, visual drawings) are highly effective in forming the concept of "I". This confirms the importance of psychological and pedagogical approaches in the personal development of 6–7-year-old children.

As a result of the conducted studies, it was found that special methodological approaches aimed at forming the concept of "I" in 6–7-year-old preschool children are highly effective. In the experimental group, indicators such as self-awareness, positive attitude towards oneself, and understanding of social roles significantly improved. This led to the strengthening of personal identity.

The following conclusions were drawn during the study:

1. The effectiveness of methodological approaches: Games aimed at self-awareness, visual drawings, and reflection techniques were effective in forming the concept of "I" in children.

2. Socio-emotional development: The level of socio-emotional development of children increased, which improved their readiness for school.

3. Recommendations for pedagogical practice: It is necessary to include methodologies aimed at forming the concept of "I" in preschool education programs and develop special manuals for educators.

On this basis, special attention should be paid to the formation of the concept of "I" in the preschool education system to ensure the personal development of children.

References:

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